

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Effect of parenting styles on academic performance of disable students in Quetta, Pakistan

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Abstract

The current study was conducted to assess various parenting styles on the basis of disable student's discernment and to evaluate the association of disable students' educational performance with parenting styles. For the presentation of theoretical model of parenting styles, Parental Authority Questionnaire was used to evaluate the three parenting styles such as authoritative, authoritarian & permissive generated on disable students' insight [1]. In this correlational study evaluating the student's performance with their communication skills, positive attitude, learning skills, creativity, study skills and educational motivation, the Academic Performance Questionnaire was used [2]. Both mechanisms were established on five point Likert balance. The areas for sample population of the study was consist of special education schools of disabled children at Quetta, Pakistan. The data was collected from two special educational institutes. The sample size was consists of 217 students with age group of 10-26 years old. The relationship between student's academic performance with parenting styles was estimated by Pearson's correlation coefficient (r). According to the findings of the present study relationship of authoritative parenting style with academic performance was found to be positive. Whereas the correlation between authoritarian and permissive parenting styles and academic performance were negatively associated. Generally, the authoritative parenting style was found to be positive parenting style and authoritarian and permissive styles were demonstrated to be negative parenting styles in the cultural perspective of Quetta.

Keywords: Parenting Styles; Authoritative; Authoritarian; Permissive; Disable; Students

1. Introduction

Parents are the key person who play very important role in the development and upbringing of their children. Different parenting techniques are positively utilized for training of their children. Young generation can play a pivotal role in the prosperity and development of nation. Positive and healthy psycho-social development is necessary for future generation, so they can be able to excel in all fields of life most importantly in education. Disabled children need more attention and positive bonding for their Psycho-social development [3]. Reportedly, about 3.28 million people in Pakistan were with various disabilities (1998 census), it was at the increase in 2015 to 4.46 Million, including 1.87 million women. This comes to almost 2.49% of the population in that year. In the recent census, the figures are further increased to 4.73 Million [4]. For this big number of handicapped individuals, there are only 531 public sector Schools for special children and about non-governmental organizations have 200schools [5].

The traditional societies like Pakistan different sociological and psychological perspectives such as education is very low and development process has yet not taken-off the pace, the individuals with disabilities are always concealed from others, especially those disabilities which are acquired at or soon after birth [6]. Physical deformities (such as limbs, vision, and deafness) and mental disorders are perceived as a humiliation. It is considered disgrace for the 'family name'

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especially for the joint family system. Any disability or handicap individual (due to psychological concerns or congenital disorder) is taken as a threat to the social status of the family [7, 8]. The families are usually concerned about the social discrimination due to other people and they conceal the facts or having of handicapped births.

In 1971 Baumrind [9] developed the theoretical model of parenting. This model was composed of three parenting styles known as; authoritative, authoritarian and permissive. These three parenting styles were based on two dimensions recognized as demandingness and responsiveness. A balance between these two dimensions like demandingness and responsiveness can be maintained by Authoritative parenting style. Responsiveness represents the warmth supportiveness while demandingness talks about the behavioral control [10]. In comparison, authoritarian parents were found to be unresponsive. Authoritarian parents are restricted to only one dimension that is demandingness while permissive parents are responsive but are not demanding.

Academic performance refers to the collection of different educational results in pupils. Performance is designated by numerous characteristics, which vary from institution to institution. Performance of the student can be indicated by its, communication skills, study skills, grades, creativity, working skills, self-realization, motivation, creative writing, attitude and self-reliance [2]. Numerous strategies are required to implement for attaining educational objectives. The selection of positive and negative strategies is reliant upon parenting style, which is responsible for training and rearing the child. Studies showed that the children reared by authoritative parents practice adaptive accomplishment stratagems which confirm low level of failure, task- irrelevant behaviour, expectations, self-enhancing attributions, and low level of passivity while youngsters who are being neglected from family sides practice maladaptive approaches which are responsible for high level of passivity, task irrelevant behaviours and lack of self-enhancing attributions [11]. Research studies showed that the students reared under positive parenting style proved to be healthy and successful [12]. Parenting can enhance the firm and positive sense of self-stem. Well cared students who are reared under best parenting styles would be resilient, socially competent and emotionally strong and such students have the capability to discover novel opportunities.

The current study endeavored to examine the association of three basic parenting styles authoritative, authoritarian and permissive with their disable children's academic performance [9].

1.1. Objectives of the study

- To find out which parenting style is prevalent among disable students.
- To observe and evaluate the effect of parenting style on academic performance of disabled students.

2. Methodology

2.1. Research design

There are two special education institutions in Quetta, Capital of Balochistan working under Government. These institutes are

- Special Educational complex killi Shabo, Quetta,
- Kiran Complex for Special education, Brewery road, Quetta.

The study samples will be collected from these institutes and purposive sampling technique will be applied.

2.2. Target Group

The respondents of the study were disable students of special education schools of Quetta, Pakistan. The participants were students of secondary level learning in Class fifth, sixth, seventh eighth, ninth and 10th of the special educational institutions. Their ages were between 10 to 26 years.

2.3. Sample size

Vital sampling techniques were applied and 217 respondents/participants interviewed for the study.

2.4. Tool for Data Collection

Two types of questionnaires were selected keeping in view the scope of this study, its objectives and hypothesis.

- Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ), developed by Buri [1] to identify different parenting styles presented by Baumrind [9].
- Academic Performance Questionnaire (APQ) which was used to measure the number of educational indicators (such as communication skills, motivation, learning capacity, positive attitude, study skills & creativity) [2].

Both questionnaires were Likert type scale ranging from intensely agrees to strongly disagree. The both measures used in study will be using interview guide, some information collected from the teachers of the disabled children to verify the truthfulness of various questions asked from the parents for better understanding.

2.5. Reliability and Validity

Researcher seeks permission for the use of questionnaire from author and consulted expert throughout questionnaire translation process. After validation, reliability of final questionnaire was tested. Finally, equipment was pilot tested to the 60 students. The Alpha Reliability for PAQ was 0.54 and for APQ 0.78 which is thought to be satisfactory.

2.6. Data Analysis

After data collection, samples were quantified and data was processed through the software SPSS (Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences).

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) was used to examine the correlation of parenting styles with academic performance as a whole and also with all indicators of performance one by one.

3. Results

In present study researcher has tried to explore the various parenting styles and its association with academic performance towards disabled students at special education schools of Quetta, Baluchistan. Authoritative parenting was found to be most significant parenting style by the observations of current study.

Before the analysis, primary data from participants was re-checked (coding and editing) to certify omission of any errors (if found). Data was analysed by using SPSS software.

Table 1 Frequency distribution of overall sample (N=217)

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	145	66.8%
Female	72	33.2%
Age (year)		
10-15	51	23.5%
16-20	155	71.4%
21-25	11	5.1%
Residential Area		
Urban	137	63.1%
Rural	80	36.9%
Family set up		
Joint	117	53.9%
Nuclear	100	46.1%

Class		
5 th	7	3.2%
6 th	31	14.3%
7 th	65	30.0%
8 th	72	33.2%
9 th	27	12.4%
10 th	15	6.9%
Number of siblings		
2	3	1.4%
3	15	6.9%
4	19	8.8%
5	46	21.2%
6	58	26.7%
7	31	14.3%
8	24	11.1%
9	19	8.8%
10	2	0.9%

3.1. Demographic characteristics

Analysis of demographics in table 1 shows the characteristics such as their age, gender, family style, residential area and educational status. Variable for determining gender demonstrates that overpowering population was male i.e. 66.8%, while remaining 33.2% were female who were interviewed as participants for present study. The age group of the respondents was 10-25 years. Among them 71.4% were of age 16-20 years, 23.5% were of age 10-15 years and lowest percentage was of 21-25 years with 5.1%. Most of the participants were resident in urban area of the city with the 63.1% while 36.9% were residing in rural area. Regarding the educational status, 3.2% were in 5th class, 14.3% were in 6th class, 30.0% in 7th class, 33.2% in 8th class, and 12.4% in 9th class and another 6.9% were in 10th class. Most of the contributors were residing in joined families i.e. approximately 53.9% whereas remaining 46.1% were belonging to nuclear family. The number of siblings of the respondents vary from 2-10. Most of the respondents have 6 and 5 siblings with the 26.7% and 21.2% respectively.

Table 2 Disability-related questions

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Onset of handicapped		
By birth	193	88.9%
After birth	24	11.1%
Disability of other family member		
Yes	64	29.5%
No	153	70.5%
Type of disability		
Physically handicapped	30	13.8%
Blind	21	9.7%
Deaf and dumb	166	76.5%

Table 2 shows the onset of handicapped, disability to other family members and type of disability. A widespread majority (88.9%) of the participants were found to having handicappers since birth, while 11.1% became handicapped after birth. Only 29.5% respondents were having any other family member who was also suffering with some disability however 70.5% were having no disability in their family. With respect to the type of disability, it was found that majority of the participants (76.5%) had victimised with deafness, almost 13.8% were physically handicapped, and 9.7% were blind.

3.2. Pearson's Correlation (r)

Correlation analysis was accomplished to explore six assumptions, which specified the negative and positive association with three parenting styles of mother and father. At First, the relationship was computed as a whole and then gender wise analysis was calculated.

Table 3 Relationship of Parenting Styles and Academic Performance Scale (n=217)

Scale	Authoritative	Authoritarian	Permissive
Academic performance	0.347***	-0.465***	0.114*
Motivation	0.274**	-0.336***	0.168*
Communication skills	0.197**	0.147*	-0.005
Learning skills	0.328***	-0.469***	0.205**
Creativity	0.461***	-0.117	0.192**
Positive attitude	0.484***	0.057	- 0.134*
Study skills	0.347***	-0.477***	0.221**

Correlation is significant at the * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$.

Table 3 indicate that an authoritative parenting style has strong positive correlation with academic performance and its indicators. Whereas it has strong negative correlation with authoritarian parenting apart from one indicator i.e. communication skills. It is also negatively associated with permissive parenting style. Yet the correlation is weak. The range of correlation co-efficient varies from 0.005 to 0.484.

Table 4 Relationship of Parenting Styles and Academic Performance Scale in females (n=72)

Scale	Authoritative	Authoritarian	Permissive
Academic performance	0.451***	-0.418***	0.174*
Motivation	0.445***	-0.447***	0.024
Communication Skills	0.399***	-0.162	-0.097
Learning Skills	0.271*	-0.418***	0.291*
Creativity	0.407***	0.019	0.150
Positive attitude	0.328**	0.014	- 0.256*
Study skills	0.385***	-0.552***	0.145

Correlation is significant at the * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$.

Table 4 shows that academic performance and its indicators have strong positive correlation with authoritative parenting. While strong negative correlation occurs between Authoritarian parenting style and academic performance with the exception of creativity and positive attitude, which have non-significant association. There is no relation between permissiveness and academic performance but two indicators i.e. learning & study skills which have weak relationship. The range of correlation co-efficient varies from 0.014 to 0.451.

Table 5 Relationship of Parenting Styles and Academic Performance Scale in males (n=145)

Scale	Authoritative	Authoritarian	Permissive
Academic performance	0.497***	-0.318***	0.219**
Motivation	0.290**	0.263**	0.132
Communication Skills	0.202*	0.145	0.024
Learning Skills	0.458***	0.138	0.214*
Creativity	0.228**	- 0.353**	0.300**
Positive attitude	0.424***	0.088	- 0.061
Study skills	0.315***	-0.248 **	0.142

Correlation is significant at the * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$.

Table 5 illustrate that the authoritative style has significant positive association with academic performance and its indicators excluding positive attitude and study skills. The Authoritarian style has negative correlation with academic performance but association is significant only for motivation. The Permissive style has generally weak relation with academic performance but relationship is significant only with motivation, learning skills and creativity. The range of correlation co-efficient varies from .024 -.458.

4. Discussion

Study was aimed to determine the association between impacts of parenting style & academic performance of disabled child. Relationship of authoritative parenting style on both child's performance and parents showed positive correlation. This positive association of authoritative parenting style on student's academic performance was proved through the result of current study. Consequences of many other studies also showed that authoritative parenting style have great impacts on child's educational performance [13]. According to the findings of Cohen [14], the psychological autonomy granting & warmth supervision characters of authoritative parenting style play key role in achievement of a high grades at school level. Certain studies have shown a positive association between academic performance of a student and authoritative parenting style [15]. Authoritative parents illustrate such a behaviour which they expect from their children. Students seek to internalize these behaviours.

Authoritative parents prove themselves as a role model for their growing children. Positive impacts of authoritative parenting style with behaviour of child have been showed by results of various studies. Authoritative parents have some fixed rules and discipline which help their children to learn about their responsibilities. Exposition of effective understanding about the emotions of authoritative parents and a significant control on them enable their children to learn and understand the emotions of the others people and also help them to handle their own situations. Children of authoritative parents develop a strong self-confidence and self-stem and they become able to accomplish things independently. These abilities and characteristics of children help them both in their practical life and also in academic performance. For promoting a good parenting style among others it is necessary to organize interactive programs among parents so that they can share their ideas about their parenting style and the best techniques to rare their children and to give awareness about positive parenting styles.

In addition to positive impacts of authoritative parents on academics performance of a child, results of certain studies have showed a negative relationship between these two factors (Parenting style & academic performance). Negative association between child's academic performance & authoritative parenting style has also being supported by results of present study. Studies of certain other researchers have also examined a negative correlation between authoritarian parents and educational performance of the students [16]. According to the findings of many researchers the children reared under authoritative parenting style strictly follow the rules displayed by their parents .They might lack a self-discipline. Authoritative parents acquire complete obedience which may discourage the independent acts of the child, as a result they may not be able to set their own personal standards & self-limits. These disabilities make such a child incompetent and unable to be a thriving student.

It is necessary to provide awareness about effective parenting styles among parents by conducting various events at schools, social gatherings and communities so that they become able to engage their children with their studies beneficially and to allow them to choose a field of their own interest and give them opportunities to prove their skills.

For the head of an institute it is recommended that they arrange different workshops for the sake of awareness about good parenting styles and also arrange PTMs. Outcomes of current study supported the hypothesis that permissive parenting style has negative relation with student's academic performance but certain other studies have shown that permissive parenting is non-significantly associated with the academic marks of the student. Results of Akhtar et al, [11] have also proved a negative relationship between student's academic achievements and permissive parenting. Researches of Inevatkina & Huver assumed a significant correlation between permissive parenting and educational achievements [17, 18]. Permissive parents have fewer expectations & demands from their children which might be a reason for lacking of self-discipline. Literature suggests that children reared under permissive parenting style show hesitance to obey the rules and regulations at school as they accomplish lack of boundaries at home.

Children of permissive parents lack social skills as such parents rarely demand a mature behavior from them. Such students have less academic motivations in comparison to their other fallows. These deficiencies of a student might be a barrier in achievement of best educational grades.

It is recommended that for better results aware the parents by good parenting styles and reconstruct the parent's role as a parent by providing them beneficial information at educational institutes, communities. For teachers it is recommended that they must be in contact with parents and aware them about the academic performance of a student and aware the parents about the effective parenting styles so they can engage their child with their education in a better way. All these activities enable the parents to take a good decision about the educational life of a child and also help them to learn and understand the good techniques to engage their children with their studies.

5. Conclusion

Consequences of present study examined a positive correlation among academic performance of disabled child and authoritative parenting style. However the educational performance was found to be negatively associated with permissive and authoritarian parenting style.

Current study was designed to address the significance of parenting styles and its correlation with academic achievements of the student in Pakistan context. Hopefully the findings of the present study would be helpful to both the parents and children to understand the impacts of good parenting on academic performance of student. Additionally outcomes of present research would be there beneficial to the school administrators, policy makers, curriculum developers and teachers to generate awareness about best parenting styles.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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